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Two Procuratorian Inscriptions from Perge

Abstract: In a recent festschrift Aşkıım Özdizbay has published two inscriptions from Perge, which require a revision. An investigation of these inscriptions and a comparison made with some inscriptions published in I.v. Perge showed that these are the bottom sections of two known inscriptions from Perge. Inscription A reads that the honouree was *praefectus praetorio* during the reigns of Claudius and of Nero. This person can only be the well known Sextus Afranius Burrus, who was the sole praetorian prefect from A.D. 50/1 to 61/2. The information related to this person was identified on a published fragment from Perge (I.v. Perge no. 222), further it is shown that Inscription A is the lower part of this already published Perge fragment. The honouree in Inscription B was a prefect in *ala Piventiana* and later became *procurator* of *provincia Galaticae et Pamphyliae* in the reigns of Claudius and Nero. The individual having these two qualifications was Lucius Pupius Praesens, who was honoured in Iconium (CIG 3991 = IGR III 263), and is known from a fragmentary inscription published in I.v. Perge no. 24. The dimensions and content of this fragmentary inscription entirely correspond with Inscription B. Therefore, Inscription B should be the lower part of I.v. Perge I, no. 24.

Aşkıım Özdizbay has recently published two inscriptions from Perge in the festschrift compiled for Haluk Abbasoğlu.¹ These inscriptions contain important – but also expected – information that provides the organization date of *provincia Lyciae et Pamphyliae* that is still considered for some a dilemma, as Özdizbay rightly emphasized. However, an epigrapher or ancient historian would no doubt feel the necessity of revising these inscriptions, since there are epigraphic problems and deficiencies in his work in respect to the identification of the honourees and in the decipherment, translation and commentary.

According to his notes, these inscriptions were uncovered «on the west of the colonnaded street, in front of insula 9» in the excavation campaigns of 2004-2005 at Perge, and they were placed on a profiled base at a later date. Though what is meant by «insula 9» is obscure in his text, it is shown at a distance of 160 m north of the Hellenistic towers, in a plan of the colonnaded street given by Heinzelmänn.² Özdizbay refers to his unpublished doctoral thesis concerning these inscribed bases, of which the measurements and descriptions are unspecified.³ He read them as follows:

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¹ A. Özdizbay, Pamphylia – Perge Tarihi ve Roma İmparatorluk Dönemi Öncesi Perge'nin Gelişimi: Güncel Araştırmalar Işığında Genel bir Değerlendirme, in: İ. Delemen – S. Çokay-Kepçe – A. Özdizbay – Ö. Turak (edd.), Euergetes. Prof. Dr. Haluk Abbasoğlu'na 65. Yaş Armağanı, vol. I, İstanbul 2008, 839–871 (esp. for inscriptions see p. 860 ff.).

² M. Heinzelmänn, Städtekonkurrenz und kommunaler Bürgersinn. Die Säulenstraße von Perge als Beispiel monumentaler Stadtgestaltung durch kollektiven Euergetismus, AA 2003, 207.

³ Özdizbay, *ibid.*, 860 with fn. 197.

Inscription A (inv. no: Ja.04.119.a-e)

Divi Claudi pro[vin]-
 CIAE Galaticae [et]
 Pamphyliae et pr[ae]
 fecto praetori Di[vi]
 Claudi et Neronis
 Claudi Caesaris
 Aug(usti) Germanici
 Ti(berius) Claudius Divi Clau-
 di L(ibertus) et Sacerdos
 Plocamus amico
 suo h(eres) c(uravit)

Inscription B (inv. no: Ja.05.212.a-e)

[c]entinae procu-
 [ra]tori Divi Claudi
 [et Ne]ronis Claudi
 [Caes]aris Aug(usti) Germa-
 nici provinciae Ga-
 laticae et Pamphy-
 liae et ALORICATA
 Ti(berius) Claudius Divi Clau-
 di L(ibertus) et Sacerdos Plo-
 camus amico suo
 h(eres) c(uravit)

The mistakes in both deciphering and translation⁴ indicate these inscriptions were not understood properly, and the epigraphical and prosopographical relationships and connections couldn't be reported on. A short investigation and comparison of its results with some inscriptions published in I.v. Perge I (IK 54) showed that these are the bottom sections of two known inscriptions from Perge:

Inscription A reads: the honouree, whose name cannot be read since it would have been on the upper section, was *praefectus praetorio* during the reigns of Claudius and Nero. This person can be no one other than Sextus Afranius Sexti filius Voltinia Burrus (PIR² A 441), who was the sole praetorian prefect from A.D. 50/1 to 61/2 and is well known from literary sources and from an inscription from Gallia Narbonensis.⁵ Therefore, the missing upper part of the inscription should include the name and other attributes of this praetorian prefect. Thus, the information related to this person was identified on a published fragment from Perge (I.v. Perge I, no. 222), further it is shown that Inscription A is the lower part of this already published Perge fragment:

⁴ The Turkish translations by Özdizbay are:

Inscription A: «Tanrılaştırılmış Claudius'a, Galatia ve Pamphylia eyaletlerine ve tanrılaştırılmış Claudius ve Nero Claudius Caesar Augustus Germanicus'un muhafız birliği komutanına, tanrılaştırılmış Claudius'un azatlısı ve rahibi Tiberius Claudius Plocamus arkadaşlarına, onun varisi olarak (bu payeyi/kaideyi) diktirdi».

Inscription B: «Tanrılaştırılmış Claudius'a ve Nero Claudius Caesar Augustus Germanicus'a, Galatia ve Pamphylia eyaletlerine, tanrılaştırılmış Claudius'un azatlısı ve rahibi Tiberius Claudius Plocamus arkadaşına, onun varisi olarak (bu payeyi/kaideyi) diktirdi».

⁵ CIL XII 5842: Vasiens(es) Voc(ontiorum) patrono Sex(to) Afranio Sex(ti) f(ilio) Volt(inia) Burro trib(un)o mil(itum) proc(uratori) Augustae proc(uratori) Ti(beri) Caesar(is) proc(uratori) divi Claudi praef(ecto) pra[e]tori(o) orname[nt]is consular(ibus).

I.v. Perge I, no. 222

H.: 0,32 m;
L.: 0,20 m;
D.: 0,22 m;
Lh.: 0,04 m.

Right, bottom and rear of the fragment are incomplete.

Photo: I.v. Perge, no. 222, Pl. L.

2] Sex. f. Vol.
proc]urat.^{vac.}

Özdizbay, Inscription A (revised)

H.: ca. 0,90-1 m;
L.: ca. 0,55-56 m;
D.: - ;
Lh.: 0,04 m.

(The measurements are estimated through the ruler in the photo).

Photo: Özdizbay 2008, 871, fig. 8)

00 -----
Divi Claudi pro[vin]-
2 ciae Galaticae [et]
Pamphyliae, et pr[ae]-
4 fecto praetori Di[vi]
Clau]di et Neronis
6 Clau]di Caesaris
Aug. Germanici,
8 Ti. Clau]dius Divi Clau]-
di l. et sacerdos
10 Plocamus, amico
suo h. c.

The honouree in Inscription B was a prefect in the *ala Picentiana* and later became *procurator* of the *provincia Galaticae et Pamphyliae* in the reigns of Claudius and Nero, as the inscription records. The individual having these two qualifications was Lucius Pupius Luci filius Sabatina Praesens, who was honoured at Iconium⁶ as the *procurator* of the province Galatia after his prefecture in the *ala Picentiana* and is known from a fragmentary inscription pub-

⁶ CIG 3991 = ILS 8848 = IGR III 263: [Κ]λαυδ[εικονιεύ]ν ὁ δῆμος ἐτείμησεν [Λε]ύκιον Πούπιον Λευ[κ]ίου υἱὸν Σαβατεῖνα [Π]ραΐσεντα, χειλίαρχον, [Ἐ]παρχὸν ἰππέων ἄλλ[ι]ς Π[ε]ικεντεινῆς, ἐπίτρο[π]ον Καίσαρος πρὸς ὀ[χ]θαῖς Τιβέρεως, ἐπίτρο[π]ον Τιβερίου Κλαυδίου [Κ]αίσαρος Σεβαστοῦ Γερ[μ]ανικοῦ καὶ Νέρωνος [Κ]λαυδίου Καίσαρος Σε[β]α[στ]οῦ Γερμανικοῦ [Γ]αλα[τ]ικῆς ἐ[π]αρχείας, τὸν ἐ[α]υτοῦ εὐεργέτην καὶ [κ]τίστην.

lished in I.v. Perge I, no. 24.⁷ The dimensions and content of this fragmentary inscription, which has only the first three lines giving the name of Lucius Pupius Praesens and some of his equestrian commissions, entirely correspond with Inscription B. Therefore, Inscription B should be the lower part of this fragmentary inscription:

I.v. Perge I, no. 24

H.: 0,32 m;
L.: 0,57 m;
D.: 0,63 m;
Lh.: 0,04 m.

Photo : I.v. Perge, no. 24,
Pl. VI.

L. Pupio L. f. Sab. Prae-
2 senti, trib. milit., prae-
fecto equitum alae
04 -----

**Özdizbay, Inscription B
(revised)**

H.: ca. 0,85 m;
L.: ca. 0, 57 m;
D.: -
Lh.: 0,04 m

(The measurements are es-
timated from the ruler in
the photo).

Photo: Özdizbay 2008, 871,
fig. 9.

00 -----
[Pi]centianae, proc[u]-
2 [ra]tore ^(sic.) Divi Claudi
[et N]eronis Claudi
4 [Caes]aris Aug. Germa-
[nic]i provinciae Ga-
6 laticae et Pamphy-
liae, et a loricata,
8 Ti. Claudius Divi Clau-
di l. et sacerdos Plo-
10 camus, amico suo
h. c.

Although these inscriptions haven't been seen by the author, their content confirms that both were statue-bases, which supported statues of Sextus Afranius Burrus and Lucius Pupius Praesens at a place on the colonnaded street of Perge. Both inscriptions seem to have been by the same hand and time. In both inscriptions the shapes and dimensions of the letters, the spacing of lines and words, and the abbreviations display similar features. The av-

⁷ L. Pupio L. f. Sab. Prae|senti, trib. milit., prae|fecto equitum alae | [P]icentianae, proc. | [C]aesaris ad ripas | [T]iberis, proc. Tiberi | [C]laudi Caesaris | [A]ugusti Germanici | [---] Prov. Galatiae | ----. Şahin restored the missing section through the inscription from Iconium (see fn. 6).

erage number of letters per line is 16 and the line spacing is ca. 1 cm. Both inscriptions were carved carefully and some letters were shaped such as \overline{M} \overline{S} \overline{A} . The letters A and V were ligatured in five places as \overline{N} (no. 1 l. 9, 10 and 12; no. 2 l. 11). The sign for abbreviations and word endings was carved as \blacktriangleright . In accord with these observations, we can examine the inscriptions under the titles below:

No. 1: Plocamus honours his friend Sextus Afranius Burrus **No. 2: Plocamus honours his friend Lucius Pupius Praesens**

	[Sex(to) Afranio] Sex(ti) f(ilio) Vol(tinia)		L(ucio) Pupio L(ucii) f(ilio) Sab(atina) Prae-
2	[Burro, tr(ibuno) mil(itum), proc]urat(ori)	2	senti, trib(uno) milit(um), prae-
	[Augustae, procurat(ori)]		fecto equitum alae
4	[Ti(beri) Caesaris, procurat(ori)]	4	[Pi]centianae, proc[u]-
	Divi Claudii pro[vin]-		[ra]torj Divi Claudii
6	ciae Galaticae [et]	6	[et Ne]ronis Claudii
	Pamphyliae, et pr[ae]-		[Caes]aris Aug(usti) Germa-
8	fecto praetori Di[vi]	8	[nici] provinciae Ga-
	Clau-di et Neronis		laticae et Pamphy-
10	Clau-di Caesaris	10	liae, et a loricata,
	Aug(usti) Germanici,		Ti(berius) Claudius Divi Clau-
12	Ti(berius) Clau-dius Divi Clau-	12	di l(ibertus) et sacerdos Plo-
	di l(ibertus) et sacerdos		camus, amico suo
14	Plocamus, amico	14	h(onoris) c(ausa).
	suo h(onoris) c(ausa).		

To Sextus Afranius Burrus, son of Sextus, (from the tribe of) Voltinia, military tribune, procurator of Augusta, procurator of god Claudius of the province Galatia and Pamphylia, praetorian prefect of god Claudius and Nero Claudius Casar Augustus Germanicus (dedicated) Tiberius Claudius Plocamus, freedman of god Claudius and priest, to his friend for the sake of his honour.

To Lucius Pupius Praesens, son of Lucius, (from the tribe of) Sabatina, military tribune, prefect of knights of Picentine Squadron, procurator of god Claudius and Nero Claudius Casar Augustus Germanicus of the province Galatia and Pamphylia, *a loricata*, (dedicated) Tiberius Claudius Plocamus, freedman of god Claudius and priest, to his friend for the sake of his honour.

no. 1, l. 2-4: The section is restored on the base of the inscription from Gallia Narbonensis, *CIL* XII 5842: ... Sex(to) Afranio Sex(ti) f(ilio) Volt(inia) Burro trib(uno) mil(itum) proc(uratori) Augustae proc(uratori) Ti(beri) Caesar(is)...

no. 2, l. 5: On stone PROC[URA]TORE. An erratum, but considering that the inscription was painted, the mistake might have been corrected by leaving the horizontal lines of E unpainted.

Sextus Afranius Burrus

This individual was the famous praetorian prefect of Nero and is well known from Suetonius, Tacitus, and Cassius Dio.⁸ An inscription from Gallia Narbonensis was dedicated to him (above fn. 5). Various inscriptions are known relating to him or to his family, but these do not provide information on his *cursus honorum*.⁹ Burrus was born in Vasio, probably in ca. 10 BC, of the tribe of *Voltinia*.¹⁰ He had already been praetorian prefect for four years when Claudius died. During the accession of the new emperor and on later occasions he played an important role together with Agrippina. When Nero acceded to the throne, Burrus took him to the praetorian soldiers to obtain their loyalty and made each soldier give the oath of allegiance. He and Seneca were the most influential pair in Nero's court. One was his counselor, the other was his sole praetorian prefect and they both had remarkable influence on the imperial decisions, also because of Nero's insouciance towards statecraft.¹¹ Cassius Dio mentions both as they were consistently together and took all the power into their hands.¹² When Burrus, following an argument in A.D. 62, was poisoned¹³ by Nero, who noticed his growing

⁸ Suetonius, Nero 35.5; Tacitus, Ann. 12.42.7 and 13.2.1; Cassius Dio 61-62. For detailed information on Sex. Afranius Burrus see: William C. McDermott, Sextus Afranius Burrus, Latomus 8, 1949, 229-54; H.-G. Pflaum, Les Carrières Procuratoriennes Equestres sous le Haut-Empire Romain, vol. 1, Paris 1960, 30-32 no. 13; PIR² A 441, s.v. Sex. Afranius Burrus; W. Eck, Afranius [3] sex. f. Burrus, sex., Der Neue Pauly I, 215; J. Schmidt, Afranius 8) Sex. Afranius Sex. f. Volt(inia) Burrus, RE I/1, 712; R. Syme, Tacitus II, Oxford 1958, 590 f.

⁹ CIL XII 1309 (Vasio): matrabus v(ota) (solvit) (libensis) m(erito) Euenos, Sex(ti) Afrani l(ibertus); CIL XI 1531 (Alto): Sex(to) A[f]ranio Burr[i] l(iberto) An[t]o vixit annis XXXV diebus XLVII [II] fecit A[f]rania Mus(a), mater pro filio; CIL VI 16963 (Via Salaria): Cn. Domitius Primigenius et Arania Burri lib(erta) C(a)enis coniuges vivi facerunt sibi et libertis libertabusq(ue) suis posterisque eorum in fronte p(edes) XXXV. h(oc) m(onumentum) h(eredes) n(on) s(equetur). One inscription from Cos contains a part of a name with Sextus Afranius, which doesn't have an exact clue to associate with Burrus, see. Inscr. di Cos ED 126: [...]ρου Κρίσ[που] ... Ἀρκε[σί]λα τοῦ Λευκ[ίου...]ΟΥΙΑΤΙΝΒΑΟΥΕ [... Σεμ]πρωνίου· Μάρκου [... Σ]έξτου Ἀφρανί[ου ... Γ]αίου Ἰουλί[ου ...]ΜΙΝΙΑΝ[...] υιοῦ [...] Μ[...]Ε[...]

¹⁰ McDermott, *ibid.*, 234 deemed 10 B.C. – A.D. 7 suitable to the birth of Burrus. However, 10 B.C. is more appropriate for one who was military tribune at the beginning of A.D. 1st century.

¹¹ J. Malitz, Nero, Cornwall 2005, 14; D. C. Arthur Shotter, Nero, New York 2005, 14 ff.

¹² Cassius Dio 61.3-4: ὅτι ὁ Πάλλας συνὼν τῇ Ἀγριππίνῃ πάντα φορτικός καὶ ἐπαχθῆς ἦν ... ὡς δὲ ἐπὶ πολὺ τοῦτ' ἐγίνετο, ἐδυσχέρανεν ὁ τε Σενέκας καὶ ὁ Βοῦρρος, φρονιμώτατοι τε ἅμα καὶ δυνατώτατοι τῶν περὶ τὸν Νέρωνα ἀνδρῶν ὄντες (ὁ μὲν γὰρ ἔπαρχος τοῦ δορυφορικοῦ ἦν, ὁ δὲ διδάσκαλος αὐτοῦ), καὶ ἔπαυσαν τὸ γινόμενον τοιαύδε ἀφορμῆς λαβόμενοι ... κατεργασάμενοι δὲ τοῦτο αὐτοὶ τὴν ἀρχὴν ἄπασαν παρέλαβον, καὶ διώκησαν ἐφ' ὅσον ἠδυνήθησαν ἄριστα καὶ δικαιοτάτα, ὥσθ' ὑπὸ πάντων ἀνθρώπων ὁμοίως ἐπαινεθῆναι. ὁ τε γὰρ Νέρων οὐτ' ἄλλως φιλοπραγματίας ἦν καὶ ἔχαιρεν ἐν ῥαστώνῃ διάγων, καὶ διὰ ταῦτα τῇ τε μητρὶ πρότερον ὑπεπεπτώκει, καὶ τότε ἠγάπα ὅτι αὐτὸς τε ἐν ἡδοναῖς ἦν καὶ ἡ ἡγεμονία οὐδὲν ἤττον διήγετο· καὶ ἐκείνοι συμφρονήσαντες αὐτοὶ μὲν πολλὰ τὰ μὲν μετερρῦθμισαν τῶν [δὲ] καθεστηκότων, τὰ δὲ καὶ παντελῶς κατέλυσαν, ἄλλα τε καινὰ προσενομοθέτησαν, τὸν δὲ δὴ Νέρωνα τρυφᾶν εἶων, ὅπως διακορῆς, ἄνευ μεγάλου τινὸς τῶν κοινῶν πάντων κακοῦ, ὧν ἐπεθύμει γινόμενος μεταβάλληται, ὥσπερ οὐκ εἰδότες ὅτι ψυχὴ νέα τε καὶ αὐθάδης ἐν τε τρυφῇ ἀνεπιπλήκτω καὶ ἐν ἐξουσίᾳ αὐτοτελεῖ τραφεῖσα οὐχ ὅσον οὐ κόρον αὐτῶν ἴσχει, ἀλλὰ καὶ ἐξ αὐτῶν τούτων προσδιαφθεῖρεται; *ibid.* 61.20.1-3: παρήλθε τε καὶ αὐτὸς ὁ Νέρων ἐς τὸ θέατρον ... καὶ αὐτῶ καὶ ὁ Βοῦρρος καὶ ὁ Σενέκας, καθάπερ τινὲς διδάσκαλοι, ὑποβάλλοντές τι παρειστήκεισαν, καὶ αὐτοὶ τὰς τε χεῖρας καὶ τὰ ἰμάτια, ὁπότε φθέγγατο τι, ἀνέσειον, καὶ τοὺς ἄλλους προσεπσπῶντο.

¹³ Tacitus, Ann. 14.5: Sed gravescentibus in dies publicis malis subsidia minuebantur, concessitque vita Burrus, incertum valetudine an veneno. valetudo ex eo coniectabatur, quod in se tumescentibus paulatim faucibus et impedito meatu spiritum finiebat. plures iussu Neronis, quasi remedium adhiberetur, inlitum palatum eius noxio medicamine adseverabant, et Burrum intellecto scelerere, cum ad visendum eum princeps venisset, adspectum eius aversatum sciscitanti hactenus respondisse: «ego me bene habeo.»

strength, Seneca stood alone and so was weakened.¹⁴ McDermott remarks the probability of that Burrus, whose ability and uprightness were unquestioned as he had no personal ambitions, was poisoned indirectly attacking Seneca through this action.¹⁵ According to these two inscriptions, by which his career can be followed, his *cursus honorum* should be as follows:

CIL XII 5842 (Gallia Narbonensis)	Inscription no. 1 (Perge)
Tribunus militum	1 Tribunus militum
Procurator Augustae	2 [Procurator Augustae]
Procurator Tiberi Caesaris	3 [Procurator Tiberi Caesaris]
Procurator Divi Claudii	4 Procurator Divi Claudii provinciae Galaticae et Pamphyliae
Praefectus Praetorio	5 Praefectus Praetorio Divi Claudii et Neronis Claudii Caes. Aug. Germ.
Consularia Ornamenta	6

1. At the beginning of A.D. 1st century he was military tribune (probably in a legion). Presumably, during this service he gained both his «excellent military fame» (*egregiae militaris famae*) and his disfigured hand (*debilis ... trunca scilicet manu*) that Tacitus records (*Ann.* 12.42 and 13.14).¹⁶
2. Then he became procurator for the private properties of Livia Augusta until A.D. 29.
3. He was procurator of Tiberius till A.D. 37, then probably procurator of Caligula until A.D. 41.
4. Presumably up to A.D. 50/1, he was procurator of Claudius. While the inscription of Gallia Narbonensis is less forthcoming, the Perge inscription informs (perhaps only some) by revealing his procuratorship for Claudius of the province of Galatia and Pamphylia.
5. He was promoted by Claudius to the highest equestrian position, *praefectus praetorio*, in ca. A.D. 50/1. He remained in this position during the reign of Nero till his death in A.D. 62, so that he held this high office alone for twelve years. Tacitus reports that Agrippina appointed him as praetorian prefect to be able to arrange her own dispositions and to render the discipline of the Praetorian Guard stricter coming under one

civitati grande desiderium eius mansit per memoriam virtutis et successorum alterius segnem innocentiam, alterius flagrantissima flagitia [adulteria]. Suetonius, Nero 35.5.8-9: Burro praefecto remedium ad fauces pollicitus toxicum misit; Cassius Dio 62.13.1-3: ... καίτοι τοῦ Βούρρου ἐναντιουμένου αὐτῷ (Nero) καὶ κωλύοντος ἀποπέψασθαι ... τοῦτον μὲν οὖν φαρμάκῳ διώλεσε...

¹⁴ Tacitus, *Ann.* 14.52.1: Mors Burri infregit Senecae potentiam, quia nec bonis artibus idem virium erat altero velut duce amoto, et Nero ad deteriores inclinabat. hi variis criminationibus Senecam adoriuntur, tamquam ingentes et privatum modum evectas opes adhuc augeret, quodque studia civium in se verteret, hortorum quoque amoenitate et villarum magnificentia quasi principem supergrederetur.; Syme, *ibid.*, 591; B. W. Henderson, *The Life and the Principate of the Emperor Nero*, London 1903, 136.

¹⁵ McDermott, *ibid.*, 253; cf. Malitz, *ibid.*, 12.

¹⁶ McDermott, *ibid.* 232.

hand.¹⁷

6. Sometime after Nero succeeded, Burrus was given the honorary rank of consul, wearing *consularia ornamenta*. McDermott remarks that Burrus might have been given the consular insignia in late 54,¹⁸ but in the Perge inscription this honorary rank doesn't appear, as this is this case, the Gallia Narbonensis inscription should be of a later date than the inscription from Perge which probably dates from the early years of Nero. So the date he gained consular insignia seems to be somewhat later than Nero's accession.

Lucius Pupius Praesens¹⁹

Praesens honoured in no. 2 was already known through an inscription from Iconium (see fn. 6), a series of inscriptions containing the boundary arrangements between Sagalassus and Tymbrianassus²⁰ and the aforementioned fragmentary Perge inscription that is examined here under No. 2 (see p. 4). According to both honorific inscriptions, his *cursus honorum* was as follows:

ILS 8848 (Iconium)

χειλίάρχος

ἑπαρχος ἰππέων ἄλλης Πεικεντεινῆς

ἐπίτροπος Καίσαρος πρὸς ὄχθαις Τιβέρεως

ἐπίτροπος Τιβ. Κλαυδίου Καίσ. Σεβ. Γερμ. καὶ
Νέρωνος Κλ. Καίσ. Σεβ. Γερμ. Γαλατικῆς ἐπ-
αρχείας

Inscription no. 2 (Perge)

1 Tribunus militum

2 Praefectus equitum alae Picentianae

3

4 Procurator Divi Claudi et Neronis Cl. Caes. Aug.
Germ. provinciae Galaticae et Pamphyliae

5 a lorica

1. He was military tribune (probably in a legion) in the 1st century A.D.
2. In his second military service, he was a prefect (probably at least as a *decurio*) in the *Ala Picentiana*.²¹ Tacitus reported that this squadron acted conjointly with the legion XVI

¹⁷ Tacitus, *Ann.* 12.42.1: Nondum tamen summa moliri Agrippina audebat, ni praetorium cohortium cura exolverentur Lusius Geta et Rufius Crispinus, quos Messalinae memores et liberis eius devinctos credebatur. igitur distrahi cohortis ambitu duorum et, si ab uno regerentur, intentiorem fore disciplinam adseverante uxore, transfertur regimen cohortium ad Burrum Afranium, egregiae militaris fama, gnarum tamen cuius sponte praeficeretur.

¹⁸ McDermott, *ibid.*, 233.

¹⁹ PIR² P 1807; Pflaum, *ibid.*, 58-63 no. 24.

²⁰ AE 1998, 1391: Ἐξ ἐπιστολῆς θεοῦ Σεβαστοῦ Γερμανικοῦ Καίσαρος Κόιντος Πετρώνιος Οὐμπερ πρεσβευτῆς καὶ ἀντιστράτηγος Νέρωνος Κλαυδίου Καίσαρος Σεβαστοῦ Γερ<μανικοῦ> καὶ Λούκ[ι]ος Πούπιος Πραίσις [ἐπί]τροπος Νέρωνος Κλαυδίου Καίσαρος Σεβαστοῦ Γερμανικοῦ ὠροθέτησαν τὰ μὲν <ἐν> δεξι<ᾷ> εἶναι Σαγαλα<σσε>ων, τὰ δὲ ἐν ἀριστερᾷ εἶναι κώμης Τυμβρια<νασσε>ων Νέρωνος Κλαυδίου Καίσαρος Σεβαστοῦ Γερμανικοῦ ἐν ἧ καὶ πέμπτον μέρος Σαγαλα<σσε>ων. For a commentary and other parallel texts see: G. H. R. Horsley – R. A. Kearsley, Another Boundary Stone Between Tymbrianassos and Sagalassos in Pisidia, *ZPE* 121, 1998, 123-9, with fn. 5; G. H. R. Horsley, *The Greek and Latin Inscriptions in the Burdur Archaeological Museum*, London 2007, 237-239 no. 336.

²¹ For *Ala Picentiana* see: C. Cichorius, *Ala*, in: *RE* I, 1257 ff.; Michael G. Jarrett, Non-Legionary Troops in Roman Britain: Part One, the Units, *Britannia* 25, 1994, 41.

Gallica against rebels of the Batavian riot in A.D. 70, but before long gave up resisting the rioters and returned to Mogontiacum.²² The squadron was attested in several diplomas²³ at Germania Superior in A.D. 74-82 and later in Britannia around A.D. 82-90.²⁴ Its presence in Britannia continued until at least A.D. 122-4 according to a diploma²⁵ and was included in a Hadrianic list of troops from Pannonia Superior.²⁶

3. Later, according to the inscription of Iconium, Praesens appears to have been ἐπίτροπος πρὸς ὄχθαις Τιβέρεως (*procurator ad ripas Tiberis*),²⁷ namely the procurator who was responsible for the elevation and strengthening the banks of Tiber in Rome against floods. There were several officials for the problems of the river Tiber and especially in times of deluges or mudslides by the river they were active in the maintenance and renovations of ports.²⁸ In the first century there were serious initiatives taken for the problems of the Tiber and of a board to be established against them.²⁹ As we learn from Suetonius, the first commissions relating to the surroundings of the Tiber damaged by floods was done by Augustus.³⁰ In A.D. 15, there were damaging deluges intensified by earthquakes and storms causing loss of life and property and Tiberius commissioned five senators in order to oversee the situation of the Tiber and to establish a permanent board for the supervision of the river.³¹ Though *procurator ad ripas Tiberis* is not known as to have worked with them³², probably he was responsible of protecting the properties of the emperor by the river, while the senators continued in their aforementioned tasks. Praesens

²² Tacitus, *Hist.* 4.62: non tulit ala Picentina gaudium insultantis vulgi, spretisque Sancti promissis aut minis Mogontiacum abeunt.

²³ AE 1910, 211; AE 1962, 290; CIL XIII 6277 and 11869.

²⁴ AE 1975, 559; CIL XVI 65 and VIII 1195.

²⁵ F. N. Fryce, *A New Diploma for Roman Britain*, *JRS* 20, 1930, 16; An undatable inscription was found in bathhouse in Malton, see D. R. Wilson, R. P. Wright ve M. W. C. Hassal, *Roman Britain in 1970*, *Britannia* 2, 1971, 252 and 291.

²⁶ AE 1930, 37 = CIL XVI 69 = AE 1931, 79; AE 1930, p. 28 no. 88.

²⁷ Pflaum, *ibid.*, 59 ff.

²⁸ DAGR 1623 f., s.v. Curatores Alvei Tiberis et Riparum et Cloacarum Urbis.

²⁹ G. S. Aldrete, *Floods of the Tiber in Ancient Rome*, Maryland 2007, 199 f.

³⁰ Suetonius, *Augustus* 30.1: aduersus in cendia excubias nocturnas uigilesque commentus est; ad coerendas inundationes alueum Tiberis laxauit ac repurgauit completum olim ruderibus et aedificiorum prolotionibus coartatum.

³¹ Tacitus, *Ann.* 1.76: Eodem anno continuis imbribus auctus Tiberis plana urbis stagnauerat; relabentem secuta est aedificiorum et hominum strages. igitur censuit Asinius Gallus ut libri Sibyllini adirentur. renuit Tiberius, perinde divina humanaque obtegens; sed remedium coerendi fluminis Ateio Capitone et L. Arruntio mandatum; Cassius Dio 57.14.7- 8: τοῦ τε ποταμοῦ τοῦ Τιβέριδος πολλὰ τῆς πόλεως κατασχόντος ὥστε πλευσθῆναι, οἱ μὲν ἄλλοι ἐν τέρατος λόγῳ καὶ τοῦτο, ὥσπερ που τό τε μέγεθος τῶν σεισμῶν ὑφ' ὧν καὶ μέρος τι τοῦ τείχους ἔπεσε, καὶ τὸ πλῆθος τῶν κεραυνῶν ὑφ' ὧν καὶ οἶνος ἐξ ἀγγείων ἀθραύστων ἐξετάκη, ἐλάμβανον, ἐκεῖνος δὲ διη νομίσας ἐκ πολυπληθίας ναμάτων αὐτὸ γεγονέναι πέντε αἰεὶ βουλευτὰς κληρωτοὺς ἐπιμελίσθαι τοῦ ποταμοῦ προσέταξεν, ἵνα μήτε τοῦ χειμῶνος πλεονάζῃ μήτε τοῦ θέρους ἐλλείπῃ, ἀλλ' ἴσος ὅτι μάλιστα αἰεὶ ῥέῃ; the name of these five senators is recorded in CIL VI 1237 = ILS 5925: C. Vibius C. f. Rufus / Sex. Sotidius Sex. f. Strabo / Libuscid(ius) / C. Calpetanus C. f. Staius Rufus / M. Claudius M. f. Marcellus / L. Visellius C. f. Varro / curator(es) riparum et alvei Tiberis / ex s(enatus) c(onsulto) termin(averunt).

³² W. Eck, *Die Verwaltung des Römischen Reiches in der Hohen Kaiserzeit*, vol. 2, Basel - Berlin 1998, 160, fn. 65.

might have taken responsibility during the great flood of A.D. 36 reported by Cassius Dio.³³ There is no information on how long he held this office or what was/were his task(s) afterwards, if there was any.

4. Praesens was commissioned as *procurator* in the province of Galatia and Pamphylia, most probably directly following Sextus Afranius Burrus who was also procurator of the same province as the honouring by Plocamus of both at the same time shows there was no other procurator between them. The senate and people of Iconium honoured Praesens for his aid in reconstruction and foundation, renaming the city Claudiconium (see fn. 6). He presumably took this commission of 100.000 sesterii³⁴ around A.D. 50/1 when Burrus became praetorian prefect, after Claudius died he continued in this position in the reign of Nero. In this period, according to some dubious inscriptions, Nero might have constructed the scene and sub-scene of the theatre at Iconium through his procurator Lucius Pupius Praesens.³⁵ Again under Nero, Lucius Pupius Praesens took his place in the boundary arrangements between Sagalassus and Tymbrinassus alongside the governor of Galatia, Quintus Petronius UMBER and his presence was due to Tymbrinassus, which belonged to the imperial patrimonium (τὰ μὲν <έν> δεξι<ῶν> εἶναι Σαγαλα<σσέ>ων, τὰ δὲ ἐν ἀριστερῶν εἶναι κώμης Τυμβρία<νασσέ>ων Νέρωνος).³⁶ As we know of that UMBER's term of office was around A.D. 54-5, so he must have been continued his procuratorship of the province Galatia at least till A.D. 55.
5. His last position recorded in the inscription of Perge is *a loricata*. There are not many inscriptions containing the word *loricata*. Certain individuals are known to us as *procurator a loricata* from some inscriptions from Rome.³⁷ These inscriptions date from A.D. 1st to 2nd centuries, those which have the expression of *Augusti liberti* are more probably from the early first century. Then, some Ephesian inscriptions record the career of a *procurator* of Trajan, Lucius Vibius Lentulus who was denoted ἀπὸ τῶν λόγων λωρεϊκάτης namely *a*

³³ Cassius Dio 58.26-27: Σέξτου δὲ δὴ Παπνίου μετὰ Κυνίου Πλαντίου ὑπατεύσαντος ὃ τε Τίβερις πολλὰ τῆς πόλεως ἐπέκλυσεν ὥστε πλευσθῆναι, καὶ πυρὶ πολὺ πλείω περὶ τε τὸν ἵππόδρομον καὶ περὶ τὸν Ἀουεντίνον ἐφθάρη, ὥστε τὸν Τίβεριον δισχίλιας καὶ πεντακοσίας μυριάδας τοῖς ζημιωθεῖσι τι ἀπ' αὐτοῦ δοῦναι.; Pflaum, *ibid.*, 59 f.

³⁴ Pflaum, *ibid.*, 62.

³⁵ IGR III 262 = SEG XXXIV 1326; transcriptions differ. M. Horster (*Bauinschriften römischer Kaiser: Untersuchungen zu Inschriftenpraxis und Bautätigkeit in Städten des westlichen Imperium Romanum in der Zeit des Prinzipats*, Stuttgart 2001, 194 fn. 16) remarks that the restoration of the emperor's name is just on account of the name of Pupius read on the inscription, and however, this is not enough for any restoration and this emperor might have been Augustus and Pupius a *legatus augusti*.

³⁶ S. Mitchell, *Anatolia: Land, Men, and Gods in Asia Minor I. The Celts and the Impact of roman Rule*, Oxford 1993, 157. For inscriptions see fn. 20.

³⁷ CIL VI 8688: C. Iulio Basso Aemiliano actori Caesaris ad Castor(em) et ad loricata(m) ad auctoritatem Heliodorus l(ibertus) fecit; 8689: T. Fl(auius) Aug(usti) lib(erto) Martiali proc(uratori)/ Augusti ad Castor(is); 8690: Gami Aug(usti) l(iberti) proc(uratori) a loricata; 8691: Hechi Aug(usti) l(iberto) pro(curatori) a loricata ex ration(e) peculiar; 8692: Orthri Aug(usti) l(iberti) proc(uratori) a loricata. Werner Eck didn't include *a loricata* in his book containing his articles on Roman administration (*Die Verwaltung des Römischen Reiches in der Hohen Kaiserzeit 1: Basel 1995; 2: Basel 1998*) at all. Likewise, he doesn't give it in his another paper in CAH XI₂, Part II. Government and Civil Administration, p. 195-266.

loricata.³⁸ Pflaum examining the Ephesian inscriptions observed that Lentulus became responsible for treasure (μονήτης – e. g. cashier) in Rome as a *centenarius*, then he firstly became procurator of *Pannonia et Dalmatia* and secondly of Asia as a *ducenarius*; later, he was back in Rome and appointed a *loricata* (probably accountant of fiscal revenues).³⁹ Likewise, Praesens returned to Rome after his procuratorship in the *provincia Galatiae et Pamphyliae* and was assigned a *loricata* by Nero. It was suggested that this office indicates a special task relating to the imperial treasury,⁴⁰ or was a title given to fiscal officials collaborated by *ad castorem* and defined by a cuirassed statue.⁴¹ The word *loricata* in the inscriptions of *CIL VI* was not related to a statue by Mommsen,⁴² but later interpreted as «the bars on the podium of temple which surrounded the *fiscus*».⁴³ Pflaum referring to a certain section from the letters of Pliny the Younger⁴⁴ and relating the cuirassed statue of Julius Caesar in front of the temple of Divus Iulius with a *loricata* remarked that this official might have been involved in the management of precious metals.⁴⁵ Corbier revised all the related documentation and the position of M. Antonius Pallas,⁴⁶ who was freed by Antonia and granted honours in A.D. 52 by the Roman Senate (these honours were displayed *ad statuam loricatam divi Iulii*, see fn. 44), in her recent publication.⁴⁷ She identified the *statua loricata divi Iulii* mentioned by Pliny the Younger with a cuirassed statue placed in the Forum of Caesar and referred in Pliny the Elder⁴⁸: the financial office of imperial administration was near this statue. She concluded that Pallas in Claudian period and Lentulus in the Trajanic period were charged with imperial finances.⁴⁹ Pallas

³⁸ AE 1924, 81 = I.v. Ephesos, no. 3046 = Smallwood, NTH 286: Λ(ούκιον) Ουείβιον Γαίου υἱὸν Αἰμιλία Λέντουλον ἐπίτροπον Αὐτοκράτορος Νέρβα Τραιανοῦ Καίσαρος Σεβαστοῦ Γερμανικοῦ Δακικοῦ, ἀπὸ τῶν λόγων λωρεϊκάτης, Ἀσίας, Παννονίας, Δαλματίας, μονήτης, ἔπαρχον εἰλης Φλαουίας β' πολειτῶν Ῥωμαίων, χιλίαρχον λεγιῶνος ζ' Γεμίνης Φιδήλεως, ἔπαρχον τεκτόνων, βοηθῶ Λ(ουκίου) Πομπηίου Οὐοπέισκου Κατελλίου Κέλερος ἑδῶν ναῶν ἱερῶν τόπων τε δημοσίων. Κλαύδιος Στρώμων, Κλαύδιος Ἐπίγονος, Κλαύδιος Εὐήμερος, Κλαυδίου Στρώμωνος υἱοὶ ἀπελευθέρου Κλαυδίου Ἀριστίωνος, τὸν ἴδιον εὐεργέτην. For other parallel texts, see Pflaum, *ibid.*, 156 ff. (no. 66, L. Vibius Lentulus); I.v. Ephesos nos. 736, 2061.

³⁹ Pflaum, *ibid.*, 157.

⁴⁰ Dictionnaire des Antiquités Grecques et Romaines, p. 812, *s.v.* Ratio, Rationalis.

⁴¹ L. Richardson, *A New Topographical Dictionary of Ancient Rome*, Baltimore 1992, 235, *s.v.* Loricata.

⁴² T. Mommsen, commentary for *CIL VI*, 8688-8692.

⁴³ J. Carlsen, *Vilici and Roman Estate Managers Until A.D. 284*, Rome 1995, 128 f.

⁴⁴ Plinius, *Epistulae* 8.6.13: Finem existimas? Mane dum et maiora accipe: 'Vtique, cum sit utile principis benignitatem promptissimam ad laudem praemiaque merentium inlustrari ubique et maxime iis locis... ea quae x kal. Februarias quae proximae fuissent in amplissimo ordine optimus princeps recitasset senatusque consulta de iis rebus facta in aere inciderentur, idque aesfigeretur ad statuam loricatam diui Iulii'.

⁴⁵ Pflaum, *ibid.*, 157; R. W. Davies, *A Note on Loricitis*, *Bonner Jahrbücher* 168, 1968, 162 and 165.

⁴⁶ For a detailed account on M. Antonius Pallas see: S. I. Oost, *The Career of M. Antonius Pallas*, *AJPh* 79/2, 1958, 113-139.

⁴⁷ M. Corbier, *Donner à voir, donner à lire - Mémoire et communication dans la Rome ancienne*, Paris 2006, 147-162 (For an older version of this study by the same author was published under the title «Pallas et la statue de César. Affichage et espace public à Rome», *Revue numismatique* 152, 1997, 11-40).

⁴⁸ Plinius, *Nat. Hist.* 34.18: Caesar quidem dictator loricatam sibi dicari in foro suo passus est.

⁴⁹ Corbier, *ibid.* 156.

was dismissed from service by Nero in A.D. 55 and Praesens seems to have been given this office following the dismissal of Pallas. Apparently, *a loricata* was an official who maintained the imperial accounts. The word *lorictitis* (a form of *loricatis*) on some papyri of military pay records from the A.D. second century is also believed to be connected to such a statue that probably stood before a chest where cash accounts were kept.⁵⁰

Tiberius Claudius Plocamus

The person, who erected the statues of his friends Burrus and Praesens, is already known from another Perge inscription.⁵¹ On that inscription, the senate and people of Perge honour Plocamus, who was once priest of the imperial cult in Iconium, because of his piety towards emperors (Claudius, Nero and perhaps later?). In order to understand the reason for Plocamus' presence in Perge, one should first consider the well directed determinations of Şahin concerning him in the commentary to I.v. Perge I, no. 35. According to Şahin, his *nomen gentilicum* and letter styles show that the date of honouring should be by the time of Claudius and Nero. After his liberation Plocamus went to his probable homeland, Claudiconium, whose name was changed in honour of Claudius and became imperial priest. Likewise, the scope of his habitation in Perge should also be related to the imperial cult that is clearly derived from the inscription that reads *διὰ δὲ τὴν εἰς τοὺς Σεβαστοὺς εὐσέβειαν καὶ τὴν ἐν αὐτοῖς κόσμιον ἀναστροφὴν*. The duration of his residence in Perge coincided with the time when Galatia was inclusive of Pamphylia (during the reigns of Claudius and Nero) and the when imperial cult was initiated at Perge. Perhaps, Plocamus was sent by the emperor in person (Claudius or Nero) to Perge for the preparations for establishing the imperial cult. The information relating to the imperial cult in Perge belongs to the period of Flavians and later. That the relations between Claudiconium, where Plocamus was formerly the priest of imperial cult, and the family of Iulii Cornuti were well-established might have played a role in presence of Plocamus in Perge for this purpose.

The connection Şahin made between the presence of Plocamus at Perge and the family of Iulii Cornuti can be built on firmer grounds from new inscriptions. It is already known that the family of Iulii Cornuti defrayed the cost of some remarkable constructions at least from the reign of Nero onwards.⁵² The best known of these is the gymnasium-palaestra complex constructed by C. Iulius Cornutus in the northwest section of Perge.⁵³ C. Iulius Cornutus was honoured by the people of Ariassus and Etenna in Perge,⁵⁴ so the family had affiliation

⁵⁰ R. O. Fink, *Roman Military Records on Papyrus*, Michigan 1971, 254-65 (Pay Records: 70); J. F. Gilliam, *Review: Documenti per la storia dell'esercito romano in Egitto* by Sergio Daris, *AJPh* 88, 1967, 101.

⁵¹ I.v. Perge I, no. 35: [ὁ δῆμος] | ὁ Πε[ργαί]ων καὶ ἡ βουλὴ [ἐτ]είμησαν [Τ]ιβέριον [Κ]λαύδιον, Σεβαστοῦ ἀπελεύθερον καὶ [ἰ]ερέα γεγονότα ἐν Κλαυδικονίῳ, Πλόκαμον διὰ δὲ τὴν εἰς τοὺς Σεβαστοὺς εὐσέβειαν καὶ τὴν ἐν αὐτοῖς κόσμιον ἀναστροφὴν.

⁵² For details see: I.v. Perge I, p. 30 ff.

⁵³ K. von Lanckoronski - E. Petersen, *Städte Pamphylens und Pisidiens I*, Wien - Prag - Leipzig 1890, no. 32a; IGR III 789 b; I.v. Perge I, no. 37.

⁵⁴ I.v. Perge I, nos. 40-41.

with other Galatian cities. The wealthy family of Iulii Cornuti took the initiative during the period of establishing the imperial cult in Perge; this is clearly understood because the first priest of the cult was from the same family. It makes sense that they took Iconium as an example, which already had the imperial cult, and Plocamus might have taken an important role during the foundation of the cult. Plocamus was both the priest of Claudius in Iconium (even perhaps initiated the imperial cult in Iconium by the order of Claudius following his liberation), and became *amicus* with *praefectus praetorio* Sextus Afranius Burrus and a *loricata* Lucius Pupius Praesens, who were rather influential men at court. Plocamus most probably became friend to them while he was priest of the imperial cult in Iconium when they were the procurators of the province. This clearly shows his strong relations with the Roman central authority. Therefore, the wealthy Iulii Cornuti family seems to have implemented the establishment of the imperial cult in Perge through the experience and effective mediation of Plocamus. After Plocamus concluded the preparations for the imperial cult, C. Iulius Cornutus Bryoninus, son of C. Iulius Cornutus, probably became the first priest of the cult.⁵⁵ Bryoninus was also honoured by his brothers and the people of other Galatian cities like Claudiconium and Conana as the priest of emperors.⁵⁶

One of the most remarkable conclusions deduced from inscriptions is the definite evidence for that Lycia and Pamphylia were not joined until Vespasianus, an idea that was firstly asserted by Brandt and later constantly argued by Şahin and Adak.⁵⁷ In both inscriptions, both procurators who were in charge by the times of Claudius and Nero, were commissioned in the *provincia Galaticae et Pamphyliae*, so it has undoubtedly been proved that Pamphylia was joined with Galatia by the reigns of Claudius and Nero, as Özdizbay also remarked.⁵⁸

⁵⁵ I.v. Perge I, no. 57.

⁵⁶ I.v. Perge I, nos. 42-45.

⁵⁷ H. Brandt, *Gesellschaft und Wirtschaft Pamphylens und Pisidiens im Altertum*, Bonn 1992, 98; S. Şahin, *Ein Vorbericht über den Stadiasmus Provinciae Lyciae in Patara*, *Lykia* 1, 1994, 130 ff.; I.v. Perge I, p. 31 fn. 49; I.v. Perge II, 138 f. no. 466. For a detailed commentary of Adak on the issue see: S. Şahin – M. Adak, *Stadiasmus Patarensis. Itinera Romana Provinciae Lyciae*, Istanbul 2007, 85-93.

⁵⁸ Özdizbay, *ibid.*, 861.

Özet

Perge'den iki Procurator Yazıtı

Kısa bir süre önce Aşkıın Özdizbay Perge'den iki adet Latince yazıtın kopyasını ve çevirisini, Prof. Dr. Haluk Abbasoğlu için hazırladıkları armağan kitabında yayımlamıştır. Verdiği bilgilere göre, bu yazıtlar 2004 - 2005 yılları Perge kazılarında, bir silmeli kaide üzerine sonradan yerleştirilmiş olarak ele geçmiştir. T. Claudius Plocamus'un onurlandırmalarını içeren metinler üzerine yapılan kısa bir araştırma ve sonuçlarının I.v.Perge (IK 54)'te yayınlanmış bazı yazıtlarla yapılan karşılaştırma, bu yazıtların bilinen iki Perge yazıtının alt kısımları olduğunu göstermektedir. Yazıt A'da onurlandırılan kişinin Claudius ve Nero dönemlerinde *praefectus praetorio* olduğunu görüyoruz. Bu kişi, Suetonius (Nero 35.5), Tacitus (Ann. 12.42.1), Cassius Dio (61.3-4; 62.13.1-3) ve Gallia Narbonensis'ten bir yazıt (CIL XII 5842) aracılığıyla bilinmekte olup, söz konusu dönemde tek başına *praefectus praetorio* olan Sextus Afranius Burrus'tur. Dolayısıyla yazıtın eksik olan baş kısmında bu kişinin künyesi olmalıdır. Nitekim daha önce yayınlanmış olan bir Perge yazıtında da (I.v. Perge I, no. 222) söz konusu kişiye ait bilgiler olduğu tespit edilmiş ve bunun Yazıt A'nın baş kısmı olduğu anlaşılmıştır. Yazıt B'de onurlandırılan kişi *ala Picentianae* birliğinde komutan olmuş ve daha sonra Claudius ve Nero dönemlerinde Galatia-Pamphylia eyaletinde *procurator* olarak görevlendirilmiştir. Bu vasıflara uygun kişi, Iconium'dan bir yazıtta (CIG 3991) Claudius tarafından Galatia eyaletinde *procurator* olarak görevlendirildiği belirtilen Lucius Pupius Praesens'tir. Daha önce yayınlanmış ve sadece ilk üç satırı mevcut olup aynı kişinin adı geçen bir Perge yazıtının (I.v. Perge I, no. 24) ölçüleri harf biçimleri, metin içeriği incelenmiş ve Yazıt B'nin üst kısmı olduğu anlaşılmıştır.